

Physico-chemical Studies on Metal Chelates of 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenoneanil (HMAA)

Y. Z. PATHAK and G. B. JOSHI

Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Bhavnagar

Manuscript received 6 May 1978, revised 28 August 1978,
accepted 22 December 1978

IN continuation of our previous communications^{2,3}, herein we describe potentiometric studies on complexes of 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenoneanil (HMAA) with Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Zn(II), Mn(II) and Cd(II) at $30 \pm 0.2^\circ$ in 60% v/v dioxane-water media at constant ionic strength maintained by adding 0.1M KNO₃. The Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique^{4,5} as used by Irving and Rossotti¹ has been applied to determine the protonation constant of the ligand and the formation constants of complexes. The log K values were computed by various computational methods. The proton-ligand stability constants determined by interpolation at various $\bar{n}_A$ values method and metal-ligand stability constants determined by least square method are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF LIGAND AND METAL COMPLEXES

Ion	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β
H	10.83	3.57	14.40
Cu(II)	8.22	6.43	14.65
Ni(II)	7.05	5.21	12.26
Co(II)	6.42	4.37	10.79
Zn(II)	7.83	5.40	13.23
Mn(II)	5.62	4.11	9.63
Cd(II)	7.74	5.30	13.04

From the values of stability constant of the metal chelates the order is $\text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+} > \text{Cd}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Mn}^{2+}$. This is in accordance with Irving and Williams order⁶. A parallelism between log K and second ionization potential of the metal ions was also observed, as had been suggested by Irving and Williams⁶.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. K. A. Thaker, Head of the Department of Chemistry for providing necessary research facilities. We are also thankful to Saurashtra University for providing the scholarship to one of us (Y.Z.P.).

References

1. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.
2. Y. Z. PATHAK and G. B. JOSHI, *J. Inst. of Chemists (India)*, (in press).
3. Y. Z. PATHAK and G. B. JOSHI, *J. I. C. S.* (in press).
4. J. BJERRUM, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution", P. Haase and Sons, Copenhagen.
5. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2003.
6. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3129.

Colorimetric Estimation of Vanadium(V) with N-o-Chlorophenylcinnamohydroxamic Acid

(Miss) S. K. AGRAWAL and V. K. GUPTA*

Department of Chemistry, Ravishankar University,
Raipur, 492.002, M. P.

Manuscript received 7 April 1977, revised 26 April 1978,
accepted 22 December 1978

N-ARYLHYDROXAMIC acids are being increasingly used as selective and sensitive reagent for vanadium(V) and other metal ions¹⁻³. It is well known that introduction of an electrophilic substituent like chlorine on the N-phenyl ring of a reagent (N-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid) reduces the stability of the metal complexes and thus increases the selectivity of the reagent¹⁰⁻¹¹. Hence N-o-chlorophenylcinnamohydroxamic acid has been synthesised and examined for the colorimetric estimation of vanadium(V) and it was found as a selective and sensitive reagent for vanadium(V). The method has been applied for the determination of vanadium(V) in B.C.S. steel.

Experimental

N-o-Chlorophenylcinnamohydroxamic Acid: The reagent was prepared from N-o-chlorophenylhydroxylamine and cinnamoylchloride by the reported method¹². All attempts to obtain N-o-chlorophenylhydroxylamine in solid state failed. Hence the hydroxylamine was prepared *in situ* and the ligand was synthesised by the earlier reported method¹³⁻¹⁴. It melted at 183° and gave the following analysis: Found N 4.84%, calcd. N 5.11%.

A 0.1% (w/v) solution of the reagent in ethanol, free chloroform, was used for all extraction work.

Standard Vanadium Solution: A stock solution of vanadium was prepared from analytical grade ammonium metavanadate by standard method.

Foreign Ions Solution: The solutions of foreign ions were prepared from reagent grade salts following the procedure of West¹⁵.

Apparatus: A Carl Zeiss UV VIS Specord and C. Z. Spekol with 10 mm matched silica cells were employed for absorbance measurements.

General Procedure: An aliquot of the standard vanadium solution containing 0.02-0.2 mg vanadium(V) was transferred into a separatory funnel and the acidity was adjusted between 4 to 7M with hydrochloric acid. 10 ml of the reagent solution was added and vanadium(V) was extracted into chloroform by the reported method⁶. Absorbance was measured at 550 nm against chloroform as a blank.

* To whom correspondence should be made.